

Study of Impact of Triglyceride and VLDL Playing on Ischemic Stroke Severity and Outcome at Tertiary Care Centre, Jaipur, Rajasthan

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Abstract:

Background: Stroke is a leading cause of morbidity and disability in Asian population. Changes in the lipid profile have been suggested as a risk factor for developing ischemic stroke. The present study was designed to evaluate the triglyceride (TG) and very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) levels of ischemic stroke and correlates it with National Institute of Health Stroke Scale(NIHSS) and prediction of outcome based on Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scoring system after 28 days from day of admission.

Material and Methods: A Hospital based Prospective Observational study included 150 Patients of Acute ischemic stroke visiting OPD and IPD of Medicine department of MGMC&H Jaipur. We estimated serum TG and VLDL levels of these patient and compare them with severity of stroke according to NIHSS scale and correlated the outcome based on Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scoring system after 28 days from day of admission.

Results: Increased TG and VLDL levels positively and significantly ($p < 0.001$) correlated with NIHSS scale. Increased TG and VLDL levels positively and significantly ($p < 0.001$) correlated with MRS scale.

Conclusion: It could be concluded that higher TG, VLDL levels can be considered as a risk factor for ischemic cerebral events and higher levels of triglyceride and VLDL is associated with the more severe stroke and poor outcome.

Keywords: Triglyceride, Very low density lipoprotein(VLDL), National Institute of Health Stroke Scale(NIHSS),Modified Rankin Scale (mRS).

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Introduction

Stroke is defined as a sudden onset of a neurological deficit caused by an acute focal injury to the central nervous system due to a vascular cause.[1] The incidence of strokes occurring every year worldwide is about 17 million and it is the second leading cause of death after coronary artery disease.[2] By 2020 in developed countries, it is predicted that stroke will be accountable for 6.2% of the total burden of illness.[3] These data put forward the need for controlling risk factors, knowledge of identifying the signs of stroke, timely reperfusion therapies and measures to improve delivery of the aforementioned resources for the best possible outcome. Ischemic strokes are

the most common ($\approx 85\%$), the rest being hemorrhagic that includes cerebral and subarachnoid ($\approx 15\%$).[4] Dyslipidemia is a known cardiovascular risk where association become more apparent in both sexes.[5] Though, the incidence of stroke in both sex is not completely elucidated. Several risk factors such as dyslipidemia, hypertension, diabetes mellitus has been recognized in stroke outcome.⁶Therefore present study is aim to estimate the serum Triglycerides and VLDL levels in cerebrovascular accident cases with the aim to see the impact of these parameters on the severity of acute ischemic stroke using National Institute of Health

Stroke Scale(NIHSS) and prediction of outcome based on Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scoring system after 28 days from day of admission.

Material and Methods

A Hospital based Prospective Observational study was planned, including 100 Patients diagnosed as Acute ischemic stroke on the basis of CT/MRI findings visiting OPD and IPD of Medicine department of MGMC&H Jaipur. We classified these patients according to severity by NIHSS scale and saw the correlation between stroke severity and serum

Triglycerides, VLDL levels and correlated the outcome based on Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scoring system after 28 days from day of admission.

Patients diagnosed with CT or MRI and more than 18 years of age were included in this study while patients taking drugs which can alter TG, VLDL levels, patients with other acute conditions like MI, DKA etc were excluded from this study.

Results

Table 1: Mean values of different variables

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation
Age(years)	64.43	7.38
NIHSS Score	10.97	9.29
MRS Score	2.53	1.72
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	302.37	117.32
VLDL (mg/dl)	60.47	23.46

Mean age of patients were 64.43 ± 7.38 years. Out of 150 patients 88(58.7%) were male while 62(41.3%) were female. Male to female ratio was 1.42. Mean NIHSS score was 10.97 ± 9.27 and mean MRS score was 2.53 ± 1.72 . Mean TG was 302.37 ± 117.32 mg/dl, and mean VLDL was 60.47 ± 23.46 mg/dl.

Table 2: Relationship between Serum Triglyceride, VLDL level with NIHSS

Variables		NIHSS Range				Total
		Mild	Moderate	Moderate to Severe	Severe	
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	<150	17(100%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	17(100%)
	151-300	38 (71.7%)	15 (28.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	53(100%)
	301-450	0 (0.0%)	30(47.6%)	33(52.4%)	0 (0.0%)	63(100%)
	>450	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2(11.8%)	15(88.2%)	17 (100%)
VLDL (mg/dl)	<30	17(100%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	17(100%)
	31-50	36 (100%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	36(100%)
	51-70	2 (5.0%)	38 (95.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	40(100%)
	>70	0 (0.0%)	7 (12.3%)	35 (61.4%)	15 (26.3%)	57 (100%)

Cross tabulation p value<0.001

Among the study subject having triglyceride level less than 150mg/dl of blood all i.e 17(100%) were in mild NIHSS range. Among the study subject having triglyceride level 151-300 mg/dl of blood 38 (71.7%) and 15 (28.3%) were in mild and moderate NIHSS range respectively. Among the study subject having triglyceride level 301-450 mg/dl of blood 30(47.6%) and 33(52.4%) were in moderate and moderate to severe NIHSS range respectively. Finally, among the study subject having triglyceride level more than 450 mg/dl of blood 2(11.8%) and 15(88.2%) were in moderate to severe and severe NIHSS range respectively. Thus, with increase in triglyceride level the NIHSS severity also increases, and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$)

Among the study subject having VLDL level less than 30 mg/dl of blood all i.e 17(100%) were in mild NIHSS range. Among the study subject having VLDL level 31-50 mg/dl of blood all i.e 36(100%) were in mild NIHSS range. Among the study subject having VLDL level 51-70 mg/dl of blood 2 (5.0%) and 38 (95.0%) were in mild and moderate NIHSS range respectively.

Finally, among the study subject having VLDL level >70 mg/dl of blood 7 (12.3%), 35 (61.4%) and 15 (26.3%) were in moderate, moderate to severe and severe NIHSS range respectively. Thus, with increase in VLDL level the NIHSS severity also increases, and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 1: Correlation between NIHSS score and Serum Triglyceride

Figure 2: Correlation between NIHSS score and Serum Triglyceride

Correlation between TG and NIHSS severity scale shows significant($p < 0.001$) positive correlation($r = 0.926$) and correlation between VLDL and NIHSS severity scale shows significant ($p < 0.001$) positive correlation($r = 0.926$).

Table 3: Relationship between Serum Triglyceride, VLDL level with MRS

Variables		MRS							Total
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	<150	12 (70.6%)	5 (29.4%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (100.0%)
	151-300	0 (0.0%)	40 (75.5%)	13 (24.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	53 (100.0%)
	301-450	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	15 (23.8%)	10 (15.9%)	30 (47.6%)	8 (12.7%)	0 (0.0%)	63 (100.0%)
	>450	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (11.8%)	9 (52.9%)	6 (35.3%)	17 (100.0%)

VLDL (mg/dl)	<30	12 (70.6%)	5 (29.4%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (100.0%)
	31-50	0 (0.0%)	30 (83.3%)	6 (16.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	36 (100.0%)
	51-70	0 (0.0%)	10 (25.0%)	22 (55.0%)	8 (20.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	40 (100.0%)
	>70	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.5%)	32 (56.1%)	17 (29.8%)	6 (10.5%)	57 (100.0%)

Cross tabulation p value<0.001

Among the study subject having triglyceride level less than 150mg/dl of blood 12 (70.6%) and 5 (29.4%) were having MRS value 0 and 1 respectively. Among the study subject having triglyceride level 151-300 mg/dl of blood 40 (75.5%) and 13 (24.5%) were having MRS value 1 and 2 respectively. Among the study subject having triglyceride level 301-450 mg/dl of blood 15 (23.8%), 10(15.9%), 30 (47.6%) and 18 (12.7%) were having MRS value 2,3, 4 and 5 respectively. Finally, among the study subject having triglyceride level more than 450 mg/dl of blood 2 (11.8%), 9 (52.9%), and 6 (35.3%) were having MRS value 4,5 and 6 respectively. Thus, with increase in triglyceride level the MRS value also increases, and this difference was statistically significant (p<0.001).

Among the study subject having VLDL level less than 30 mg/dl of blood 12 (70.6%) and 5 (29.4%) were having MRS value 0 and 1 respectively. Among the study subject having VLDL level 31-50 mg/dl of blood 30 (83.3%) and 6 (16.7%) were having MRS value 1 and 2 respectively. Among the study subject having VLDL level 51-70 mg/dl of blood 10 (25.0%), 22 (55.0%) and 8 (20.0%) were having MRS value 1,2 and 3 respectively.

Finally, among the study subject having VLDL level more than 70 mg/dl of blood 2 (3.5%), 32(56.1%), 17 (29.8%) and 6 (10.5%) were having MRS value 3,4,5 and 6 respectively. Thus, with increase in VLDL level the MRS value also increases, and this difference was statistically significant (p<0.001).

Figure 3: Correlation between TG and MRS score

Figure 4: Correlation between VLDL and MRS score

Correlation analysis between serum triglyceride and MRS shows that MRS is significantly p value <0.001 positively correlated ($r = 0.949$) with triglyceride. Correlation analysis between serum VLDL level and MRS shows significant (<0.001) positive correlation with VLDL with $r = 0.949$.

Discussion

Stroke bears colossal neurological disease burden, as evidenced by emerging and expansive epidemiological literature. Stroke is the second most common cause of death worldwide, preceded only by ischemic heart disease, and the third most common cause of disability. In India, the Indian Global Burden of Disease Study 1990--2019 estimated that stroke was the largest contributor to disability adjusted life years (DALYs), and a chief contributor to deaths caused by neurological disorders. The total neurological disorder DALYs contributed by stroke was determined to be 37.9% [95% uncertainty interval 29.9--46.1]. The Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors Study (GBD) 2019 indicated that the vast proportion of stroke burden is borne by low and middle-income countries, with the age standardized death rates and DALYs being four times higher in World Bank low-income countries.[7] Impaired lipid profile is related to endothelial dysfunction and impaired vascular tone that could contribute to ischemic changes and cause areas of edema. However, there is a paucity of scientific literature studying lipid profile in Ischemic stroke patients (AIS). Identifying the changes in lipid profile could aid in the timely diagnosis and management of such patients and help formulate targeted efforts to mitigate the risk of AIS. Therefore, the present study was aimed to evaluate the impact

of TG, VLDL on the severity of acute ischemic stroke using National Institute of Health Stroke Scale(NIHSS) and to predict the outcome based on Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scoring system after 28 days from day of admission.

In this study we included 150 patients of ischemic stroke and categorize these patients according to severity with help of NIHSS scale and predicted outcome with the help of Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scoring system. We estimated the Serum Triglyceride levels and VLDL levels in all these patients and find out association of these parameter with severity of disease (NIHSS scale) and outcome of disease(mRS score).Mean age of this study was 64.43 ± 7.38 years. Out of 150 patients 88(58.7%) were male while 62(41.3%) were female. It means male female ratio of this study was 44:31. This shows male preponderance of ischemic stroke. Range of NIHSS score is from 0 to 42. Minimum score is 0 and maximum score is 42. When we take mean of NIHSS score we found Mean NIHSS score 10.97 ± 9.27 and Range of MRS score is between 0 to 6. Mean MRS score in this study was 2.53 ± 1.72 . In this study mean TG was 302.37 ± 117.32 mg/dl and mean VLDL was 60.47 ± 23.46 mg/dl.

According to NIHSS scale maximum patients 55(36.7%) had mild stroke followed by 45(30%) had moderate stroke, 35(23.3%) had moderate to severe stroke while 15(10%) patients had severe stroke in this study. We categorizes TG into small groups of <150 mg/dl, 151-300 mg/dl, 301-450mg/dl and >450 mg/dl respectively. Out of 150 patients maximum 63 patients had TG levels between 301-450 mg/dl followed by 53 patients who had TG levels 151-300mg/dl, 17 patients had TG levels >450

mg/dl and 17 had TG levels <150 mg/dl. When we saw the relationship of these groups of TG levels with NIHSS scale in these patients we found Out of 17 stroke patients who had TG levels <150 mg/dl all 17(100%) were in mild NIHSS range. Out of 53 stroke patients who had TG levels between 150 - 300mg/dl 38(71.7%)were in mild NIHSS range while 15 (28.3%) were in moderate NIHSS range respectively. Out of 63 stroke patients who had TG levels between 301 - 150mg/dl 30(47.6%) were in moderate NIHSS range while 33(52.4%) were in moderate to severe NIHSS range respectively. Out of 17 stroke patients who had TG levels between > 450 mg/dl 2(11.8%) were in moderate to severe NIHSS range while 15(88.2%) were in severe NIHSS range respectively. When we saw correlation between TG level and NIHSS scale by Pearson correlation we found significant positive correlation($p < 0.001$) which shows as TG levels increases severity of stroke increases or we can say more severe stroke correlates with higher levels of TG. Similarly, when we correlate these TG groups with mRS score we found out of 17 patients who had TG levels < 150 mg/dl 12 (70.6%) patients recovered fully and had mRS score 0 while 5 (29.4%) patients had some symptoms with mRS score 1. Out of 53 patients who had triglyceride level 151-300 mg/dl 40 (75.5%) patients had few symptoms with mRS score 1 while 13 (24.5%) patients had mild disability with mRS 2, Out of 63 patients who had triglyceride level 351-450 mg/dl 15 (23.8%) patients had mild disability with mRS score 2, 10(15.9%) patients had moderate disability with mRS score 3. 30 (47.6%) patients had moderate severe disability with mRS score 4 while 18 (12.7%) patients had severe disability with mRS score 5. Out of 17 patients who had triglyceride level >450 mg/dl 2 (11.8%), patients had moderate to severe disability with mRS score 4, 9 (52.9%) patients had severe disability with mRS score 5 while 6 (35.3%) patients died within 28 days of stroke with mRS score 6. Correlation analysis between serum triglyceride and mRS shows that mRS is positively correlated with triglyceride with r score 0.949 and this correlation was statistically significant with p value <0.001. It shows poor outcome or poor recovery with increased levels of TG.

We categorizes VLDL into small groups of <30 mg/dl, 31-50 mg/dl, 51-70mg/dl and >70 mg/dl respectively. Out of 150 patients maximum 57 patients had VLDL levels >70 mg/dl followed by 40 patients who had VLDL levels 51-70 mg/dl, 36 patients had VLDL levels 31-50 mg/dl and 17 had VLDL levels <30 mg/dl. When we saw the relationship of these groups of VLDL levels with NIHSS scale in these patients we found Out of 17 stroke patients who had VLDL levels <30 mg/dl all 17(100%) were in mild NIHSS range. Out of 36 stroke patients who had VLDL levels between 31-50 mg/dl all 36 (100%) were in mild NIHSS range. Out of 40 stroke patients who had VLDL levels between 51-70 mg/dl 2

(5.0%) were in mild NIHSS range while 38 (95.0%) were in moderate NIHSS range. Finally among the study subject having VLDL level >70 mg/dl 7 (12.3%), 35 (61.4%) and 15 (26.3%) were in moderate, moderate to severe and severe NIHSS range respectively. When we saw correlation between VLDL level and NIHSS scale by Pearson correlation we found significant positive correlation($p < 0.001$) which shows as VLDL levels increases severity of stroke increases or we can say more severe stroke correlates with higher levels of VLDL. Similarly, when we correlate these VLDL groups with mRS score we found out of 17 patients who had VLDL levels < 30 mg/dl 12 (70.6%) patients recovered fully and had mRS score 0 while 5 (29.4%) patients had some symptoms with mRS score 1. Out of 36 patients who had VLDL level 30-50 mg/dl 30 (83.3%) patients had few symptoms with mRS score 1 while 6 (16.7%) patients had mild disability with mRS 2. Out of 40 patients who had VLDL level 50-70 mg/dl 10(25.0%) patients had some but no significant disability with mRS score 1, 22 (55.0%) patients had mild disability with mRS score 2, 8 (20.0%) patients had moderate disability with mRS score 3. Out of 57 patients who had VLDL level >70 mg/dl 2 (3.5%) patients had moderate disability with mRS score 3, 32(56.1%) patients had moderate to severe disability with mRS score 4, 17 (29.8%) patients had severe disability with mRS score 5 while 6 (10.5%) patients died within 28 days of stroke with mRS score 6. Correlation analysis between serum VLDL level and mRS shows that mRS is significantly positively correlated with VLDL with r score 0.949 and p value <0.001. It shows poor outcome or poor recovery with increased levels of VLDL.

We found very few studies supporting our data one of the study is in which similar results found conducted by Simundic et al [8] in 2008 in their study they divided stroke cohort into two groups according to their NIHSS score. The group of patients experiencing moderate neurological deficit with NIHSS score <16 and of patients suffering from substantial neurological deficit with NIHSS score >16. Serum concentrations of triglycerides differed significantly between patients with different stroke severity. Patients with more severe stroke had higher serum triglycerides (OR 2.755, CI 1.0540–7.2027; $ps < 0.030$). A study by Sibel Ciplak et al [9] in 2023 found higher TG levels in the patients of stroke (200 ± 125 mg/dL) in comparison to the control group ($p < 0.05$). Significant discrepancies were found between the two groups in lipids and other key laboratory parameters. A contrast study by Zheng Li, MD et al [10] in 2020 confirmed that low level of TG resulted in severe stroke. TG had the impact on the stroke severity. Another contrast study conducted by Tomasz Dziedzic et al [11] in 2004 found that lower TG level was associated with more severe stroke as measured by Stroke severity scale on admission but they did not find a significant difference in 3-month mortality

between patients with TG <2.3 mmol/L and those with TG >2.3 mmol/L. Another study by Christopher J Weir et al [12] in 2003 found that lower triglyceride level ($p < 0.0001$) independently predicted higher mortality; early resolution of symptoms ($p = 0.005$) independently predicted lower mortality. These contrast results in different studies found may be due to difference in sample collection timing as we collected the blood sample within 2 hours of admission of stroke patient while other studies takes 24-48 hrs after admission. We did not prescribe anything orally to the patient of stroke and half-life of triglyceride is 4-6 hours so delay in sample collection might be the factor which may affect the results.

Probable mechanism of correlation of TG and ischemic stroke may be formation of atherosclerosis. Small plaques peeling off from unstable atherosclerotic plaques may embolize the intracranial arteries and cause artery-to-artery embolic stroke. Atherosclerosis occurring in certain crucial vessels may also produce an in situ thrombus and cause ischemic stroke. Notably, asymptomatic carotid stenosis has been recognized as a well-documented risk factor for stroke, and prophylactic carotid endarterectomy can decrease the risk.[13] In hypertriglyceridemia, LPL-mediated hydrolysis of TRLs may elevate the concentrations of free fatty acids (FFAs) in the proximity of the endothelium and in the systemic circulation, enhancing endothelial injury, inflammation, and atherosclerosis.[14] Another explanation may be elevated blood viscosity may promote atherosclerotic development by increasing the platelet adhesion to the sub-endothelium and protein infiltration into the arterial wall, and altering local shear forces at the sites of atherogenesis.[15] Elevated plasma viscosity may also lead to athero-thrombosis due to impaired microcirculatory flow, increased shear stress damage at the blood-endothelial interface, enhanced interactions of plasma protein with the endothelium in poststenotic recirculation zones, and an increased propensity of thrombosis.

Conclusion

In ischemic stroke VLDL and triglyceride are well established predictors of severity on a long run. In this study we studied the association of VLDL and Triglycerides with the severity of acute ischemic stroke using National Institute of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) and prediction of outcome based on Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scoring system after 28 days from day of admission. It was found that the triglyceride level and VLDL level are all positively significantly correlated to both NIHSS and mRS indicating that severity and outcome at 28 days may be well predicted with increase serum level of these parameters.

Though difference in timing of collection of samples may have caused the difference in the finding of serum triglycerides in other studies. But a definite

indication has been provided by our study. So a proactive measure can be taken as soon as their level increases, to reduce the severity and improve outcome of acute ischemic stroke. Though further studies may be required with larger study sample size to further generate evidence to confirm our findings.

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